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Research Article

Development And Validation Of A UV Spectrophotometry Method For Gemfibrozil In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms

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ABSTRACT

A new, simple, accurate, rapid and precise spectrophotometric method has been developed for validation of Gemfibrozil (GEM) in bulk drug. An attempt was made to preclude the use of corrosive inorganic solvents by the use of 1 M NaOH. The developed method was the measurement of absorptivity at 274 nm. The results of analysis have been validated as per ICH guidelines. The concentrations of this drug were evaluated in laboratory mixture and marketed formulation. Accuracy was determined by recovery studies from marketed formulation and ranges from 99.63 – 100.93%. Precision of method was found out as repeatability shows the values within acceptable limit.

INTRODUCTION

Gemfibrozil (GEM) is a dimethylphenoxy derivative 5-(2,5-dimethylphenoxy)-2,2-dimethylpentanoic acid (fig.-1). It is a lipid regulating agent used in the treatment of hyperlipidemia. Similar to clofibrate, it is used to treat hyperlipoproteinemia and as a second-line therapy for type IIb hypercholesterolemia. Gemfibrozil increases the activity of extrahepatic lipoprotein lipase (LL), thereby increasing lipoprotein triglyceride lipolysis. It does so by activating Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-alpha (PPAR α) 'transcription factor

ligand', a receptor that is involved in metabolism of carbohydrates and fats, as well as adipose tissue differentiation. Chylomicrons are degraded, VLDLs are converted to LDLs, and LDLs are converted to HDL. This is accompanied by a slight increase in secretion of lipids into the bile and ultimately the intestine. Gemfibrozil also inhibits the synthesis and increases the clearance of apolipoprotein B, a carrier molecule for VLDL. Well absorbed from gastrointestinal tract (within 1-2 hours). Gemfibrozil mainly undergoes oxidation of a ring methyl group to successively

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form a hydroxymethyl and a carboxyl metabolite. Approximately seventy percent of the administered human dose is excreted in the urine, mostly as the glucuronide conjugate, with less than 2% excreted as unchanged Gemfibrozil. Half life of the drug was 1.5 hrs and more than 95% of the drug was bound to plasma.

gemfibrozil

Fig-1. Structure of Gemfibrozil

Chemical name: 5-(2, 5-dimethylphenoxy)-2, 2-dimethylpentanoic acid

Chemical formula: C¹⁵H²²O³

EXPERIMENTAL :

Instrumentation :

UV experimentation was performed on Shimadzu 1800 UV-visible spectrophotometer equipped with Photo Diode Array (PDA) detector, with 1 cm quartz cell. Citizen Digital Ultrasonic Cleaner was used for solubility purpose.

Fig.2 Spectrum Of Gemfibrozil At The Wavelength 274

STUDY OF LINEARITY CURVES :

The aliquot portions of standard stock solutions of Gemfibrozil was diluted appropriately with 1M NaOH to get a series of concentration from 10-50µg/mL for drug. The absorbance of this drug

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

All reagents used are AR grade and gemfibrozil was gift sample obtained from flamingo Laboratories, mumbai and were used as reference standard. The tablet formulation was purchased from local market.

Preliminary solubility study :

Solubility of drug was determined at 27 ±1°C. Gemfibrozil (10mg) was added in 10 ml volumetric flask and 10ml of 1M NaOH was added in it. The clear solution of Gemfibrozil was obtained.

Preparation of standard stock solutions:

Gemfibrozil standard stock solution: (1000µg/ml). An accurately weighed Gemfibrozil (10mg) was added in 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 1M NaOH and volume was made up to the mark using 1M NaOH to get final concentration(1000µg/ml).

Study of spectra and selection of wavelength:

The aliquot portions of standard stock solutions of Gemfibrozil were diluted appropriately with 1M NaOH to obtain concentration 10 µg/mL of drug. The solutions shown in Fig. 2. From the spectrum wavelength selected for estimation of drug was 274.nm as λ max of Gemfibrozil.

was measured at 274nm respectively and calibration curve was plotted as concentration versus absorbance

Linearity and Range :

The suitable aliquots was taken to obtain 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 (1000µg/ml) stock solution. The results are shown in fig. no. 3,

Fig 3-linearity curve of Gemfibrozil

Gemfibrozil obeyed linearity in the concentration range of 10-50 µg/ml respectively at λ max 274 nm with correlation coefficient (r2 > 0.99) in this case. Marketed brand of tablet was analyzed.

Analysis of Marketed Formulation by Proposed Method:

20 capsule was accurately weighed, and reduced to fine powder. An accurately weighed powder sample equivalent to 10 mg of gemfibrozil was

transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and 1M NaOH was added in it. Sonicate it for 20 min. The solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper no. 41. The filtrate was further diluted with 1M NaOH to get final concentration (1000µg/ml). From this solution 10µg/ml was prepared. The absorbance of sample solution was measured at 274 nm and the result is shown in Table No. 1.

Table No. 1: Results of Application of Proposed Method for Analysis of Marketed Formulation

Sample	Label Claimed	% Label Claim* ± SD	% RSD
Lopid 300mg	Gemfibrozil 300 mg	99.66±1.05	1.05

VALIDATION METHOD

Accuracy

Accuracy of each of the proposed method was ascertained on the basis of recovery studies

performed by standard addition method as shown in the table no.2.

Table no.2 Accuracy study -

Sr. no.	Level (%)	Amt. taken (µg/ml)	Amt. Added (µg/ml)	Absorbance Mean* ± S.D.	Amt. recovered Mean *±S.D.	%Recovery Mean*± S.D.
1	80	30	24	0.1430±0.00094	24.22 ± 0.10	100.93 ± 1.60
2	100	30	30	0.179 ± 0.00047	29.89 ± 0.19	99.63 ± 0.64
3	120	30	36	0.214 ± 0.00081	35.33± 0.33	98.15± 0.93

*mean of each 3 reading

Precision

Precision of the analytical method is expressed as the series of the measurement. It was ascertained

by replicate estimation of the drug by the proposed method as shown in table no.3.

Table no.3 Precision-

Conc. (µg/ml)	Inter day			Intra Day		
	Mean*± S.D.	Amt. Found	% Amt. Found	Mean*± S.D.	Amt. Found	%Amt. Found
20	0.053±0.001	18.11	90.65	0.051±0.001	17.22	86.11
30	0.091±0.001	30.56	101.85	0.092±0.001	30.89	102.96
40	0.120±0.001	40.44	101.15	0.121±0.001	40.56	101.39

*mean of each 3 reading

Repeatability:

Repeatability was ascertained by getting the sample analyzed by different analyst and carrying

out analysis for no. of times. The results are shown in table no. 04

Table no.4 Repeatability study-

Sr. No.	Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance	Amt. Found	% Amt. Found
1	30	0.090	30.33	101.11
2	30	0.091	30.67	102.22
3	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
4	30	0.090	30.33	101.11
5	30	0.090	30.33	101.11
6	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
7	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
8	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
9	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
10	30	0.092	31.00	103.33
	Mean	0.091	30.74	102.47
	S.D.	0.000916	0.3054	1.018051
	%RSD	0.0100	0.0099	0.0099

Label Claim:

Brand Name: LOPID			Company: PFIZER LTD.	
Amt taken (mg)	Conc. (µg/ml)	Absorbance	Amt found	%Label Claim
14	30	0.090	8.96	99.56
14	30	0.091	9.00	100.00
14	30	0.091	8.98	99.78
14	30	0.091	9.02	100.22
14	30	0.091	9.04	100.44
14	30	0.092	9.02	100.22
	Mean	0.091	9.00	100.04
	SD	0.000916	0.03	0.33
	%RSD	0.0100	0.33	0.33

RESULT AND DISCUSSION :

The method was optimized with view to develop a rapid, simple, accurate method for validation of Gemfibrozil in bulk & pharmaceutical formulation. uv scanning at 400-200nm of Gemfibrozil shows that 274 nm is the suitable wavelength for detection of drug.(fig.2).Gemfibrozil shows linearity in the concentration range of 10-50µg/ml (r²-0.993) respectively .recovery study of drug were carried out for the accuracy parameter this study where carried out at three levels(80%, 100%, 120%) by standard addition method. The mean recovery was found to be 99.41% for Gemfibrozil respectively. The developed method was found to be simple, precise, specific, & accurate Therefore this method can be applied for routine analysis of drugs in formulation & in bulk drug.

CONCLUSION :

The developed method is suitable for validation of Gemfibrozil in pharmaceutical dosage form is accurate, precise, robust and rapid. Therefore this method can be applied for routine analysis of drugs in formulation & bulk drug.

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Books and Textbooks

2. "Spectrophotometry & Spectrofluorimetry: A Practical Approach" by Jim Hollas - This

book provides practical insights into spectrophotometric techniques.

3. "Pharmaceutical Analysis: A Textbook for Pharmacy Students and Pharmaceutical Chemists" by David G. Watson - It covers various analytical techniques including UV spectrophotometry.
4. "Principles of Instrumental Analysis" by Douglas A. Skoog, F. James Holler, and Stanley R. Crouch - A comprehensive textbook on instrumental methods of analysis, including UV spectrophotometry.

Journals and Articles

5. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research (IJPSR) - Look for articles on method development and validation of analytical techniques.
6. Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis - Offers numerous research papers on analytical methods for pharmaceuticals.
7. Analytica Chimica Acta - A journal that publishes papers on analytical chemistry, including UV spectrophotometric methods.

Specific Articles and Papers

8. "Development and Validation of UV Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Gemfibrozil in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form" - Look for similar titles in databases like PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar.
9. "Spectrophotometric Determination of Pharmaceuticals in Dosage Forms: A Review" - Reviews can provide comprehensive overviews and methodological insights.
10. "Analytical Method Development and Validation: A Concise Review" by Shrivastava and Gupta, published in the Journal of Advanced Scientific Research.

Regulatory Guidelines

11. ICH Q2(R1): Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology - This guideline provides comprehensive

instructions on the validation of analytical methods.

12. United States Pharmacopeia (USP) - The USP provides general chapters on analytical method validation.
13. European Pharmacopoeia - Contains relevant sections on analytical method validation.

Online Databases

14. PubMed - A free search engine accessing primarily the MEDLINE database of references and abstracts on life sciences and biomedical topics.
15. ScienceDirect - A leading full-text scientific database offering journal articles and book chapters from more than 2,500 peer-reviewed journals and more than 11,000 books.

16. Google Scholar - Provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature across many disciplines and sources.

Research Institutions and Organizations

17. American Chemical Society (ACS) - Provides access to a wealth of research articles and resources in the field of chemistry.
18. Royal Society of Chemistry (RSC) - Offers numerous publications and resources on analytical chemistry.

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